

SEEDRL: Smart Energy Efficiency using Deep Reinforcement Learning for 6G Networks

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Abstract—The rapid increase in mobile network traffic has led to the dense deployment of network cells and the introduction of technologies such as massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (m-MIMO) to achieve high gain and spectral efficiency. However, these benefits come with a significant growth in Operational Expenditure (OPEX) and energy consumption, which remains a major challenge in beyond 5G and 6G networks. In this paper, we employ Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques to efficiently switch off cells and mute MIMO antenna elements at some specific times to achieve a higher gain in terms of Energy Saving (ES) and the number of network changes without majorly affecting user satisfaction. Through extensive experiments, we demonstrate that our proposed method called Smart Energy Efficiency using DRL (SEEDRL) saves power by 8.99% and significantly reduces the number of ES state changes by 22.83% compared to its counterpart the threshold-based algorithm.

Index Terms—6G, Deep Reinforcement Learning, Energy Efficiency, m-MIMO, Antenna Muting.

I. INTRODUCTION

The exponential surge in mobile data traffic presents a formidable challenge for Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) on how to scale their networks to meet this demand growth. To tackle this issue, MNOs have begun large-scale deployment of 5G New Radio (NR) small cells coupled with massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (m-MIMO) antenna panels in close quarters, aiming to deliver high-throughput transmission links. While these technologies boost peak data rates, they also contribute to a considerable increase in overall energy consumption, thereby expanding both Operational Expenditure (OPEX) and carbon dioxide footprint. This escalation of emissions constitutes another hurdle for MNOs in an era where various industry sectors strive to fulfil their minimum carbon emission policies [1].

According to the survey in [2], the Radio Access Network (RAN) domain within mobile networks is the primary contributor to energy consumption, prompting the necessity for innovative solutions and technologies that lead to lower energy usage and carbon dioxide emission reduction. Among the components within the RAN, the Radio Unit (RU) is the most significant energy consumer, accounting for approximately 40% of the RAN's energy consumption—a figure higher than all other RAN components and air conditioning systems. With the ongoing implementation of m-MIMO and small cells alongside the projected surge in data traffic spurred by the introduction of beyond 5G and 6G networks, a substantial escalation in energy consumption is anticipated. To address this, The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) in its RAN1 working group has highlighted Energy Saving (ES) solutions for 5G new radio (NR) in Release 18 [3]. Multiple energy-saving techniques spanning time, frequency, and spatial domains have been explored for NR to optimize power consumption. Specifi-

cally, modulating the number of m-MIMO antenna elements in response to variations in traffic demand has emerged as a crucial strategy in the spatial domain. This approach is critical given the substantial impact of m-MIMO antennas on the overall energy consumption of network infrastructure. The Open RAN Alliance (O-RAN) has also earmarked techniques such as carrier/cell switch-off and m-MIMO antenna element switch-off as central components of its energy-saving strategy in its energy efficiency feature plan [4]. Energy saving (ES) remains a focal point in the upcoming 3GPP Release 19, where the focus is on exploring new study items related to energy efficiency as service criteria in the 3GPP SA1 working group [5]. This ongoing commitment to ES is underscored by the approval of a new study item in the 3GPP SA2 working group for Release 19, dedicated to investigating enhanced 5G network architecture that supports advanced network energy-saving techniques. Furthermore, this initiative aims to introduce energy control metrics to consumers, fostering energy-conscious service consumption [6]. These advancements mark continued efforts to enhance energy efficiency and empower consumers with more control over their energy usage, aligning with broader initiatives to mitigate the environmental impact of network technologies.

Our objective in this paper is to curtail energy consumption by transitioning cells into lower ES states based on traffic demand while preserving per-user throughput rates in a Single-User MIMO (SU-MIMO) system with two carriers. We establish two primary ES States (ESS): cell switch-off and m-MIMO Transmit Antenna Muting (TAM). Our approach centres on training a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) agent to make ESS decisions for each cell. Through a comprehensive set of simulation experiments, we demonstrate the superior performance of our solution over traditional threshold-based methods, achieving an 8.99% reduction in power consumption and a 22.83% decrease in ESS changes.

The paper is structured as follows. The related work is discussed in Sec. II, followed by the system model in Sec. III. The problem statement, along with the proposed DRL-based algorithm are presented in Sec. IV. The numerical results are reported in Sec. V. Finally, Sec. VI draws the conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

Energy consumption in mobile networks has been growing immensely as a result of the unprecedented amount of network traffic generated by newly emerging resource-hungry applications and the massive number of network users. In this vein, a sizeable body of research has been conducted on ES in mobile networks [1, 7–14]. Furthermore, standardisation work from 3GPP have included enhancements on ES as a key feature in

Release 18 [3], and it continues to be an important item for upcoming Release 19 [5].

Authors in [7, 8] employ RL techniques in the RAN, aiming to reduce energy consumption by switching off Base Stations (BSs) at particular times. The main objective of the work is to reduce energy consumption while meeting user demands taking into account KPIs from both network and UEs. A Deep Learning (DL)-based method is proposed in [1] aiming to reduce energy consumption by activating a sub-set of antennas in MIMO systems. DL is used to achieve a sub-optimal solution in a reasonable time. The study conducted in [9] uses TAM technique in multi-user MIMO networks to selectively utilise a sub-set of antennas in the BS that can meet user throughput requirements while at the same time reducing energy consumption in the BS to its lowest extent. The problem is modelled using combinatorial optimisation techniques and a Neural Network (NN) model is proposed to tackle the scalability issue of the proposed model.

Recently, a joint study of antenna selection and hybrid beamformer has gained significant interest. The study by Zhain et al [10], proposes a new method for transmit precoding and antenna selection, able to maximise system throughput and reduce system complexity. Similarly, the authors in [11] present a novel method for designing beamforming vectors at the mobile station and antenna selection at the BS side jointly. The problem is divided into three sub-problems to reduce the complexity of the problem and then each is solved using optimisation techniques. Another study by Li et al. [12] proposes a method that uses augmented antenna diversity to compensate for accuracy loss caused by low-resolution phase shift implementations.

Frenger et al. in [13] propose a dynamic m-MIMO TAM algorithm to scale down m-MIMO array size from 64TR to 32TR, 16TR and 8TR. However, different m-MIMO TAM configurations are applied based on a fixed cell utilisation threshold. Further to this study, a coordinated beamforming technique is presented in [14] for a distributed antenna system where some antennas are muted.

Different from the above-presented works, we study m-MIMO antenna element muting and cell switch-off jointly within an environment with two carriers where one carrier is used as the coverage layer and the other as the capacity layer. The traffic demand on both carriers is taken into account for the optimal ESS for cells in the capacity layer. Moreover, we consider RUs with a co-located single array of m-MIMO antenna elements instead of distributed antenna systems. Furthermore, we propose a DRL-based solution which is dynamic and adaptable to different levels of load as opposed to the static threshold-based methods.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

In this paper, we introduce a model for a wireless network that consists of B gNodeBs, denoted as $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_B\}$. Each gNodeB includes three distinct sectors, labelled as $S_{i,j}$, where i represents a sector and j signifies a gNodeB. We define $\mathcal{C} = \{C_0, C_1, \dots, C_K\}$ as the set encompassing all cells that can be hosted by each sector in a gNodeB. In this context, $C_{k,i,j}$ specifies cell k within sector i of gNodeB j . Each cell in the deployment $C_k \in \mathcal{C}$, operates on a unique frequency band, f_k , accompanied by a bandwidth BW_k .

Fig. 1: UE Arrival Rate Illustration for the Traffic Model

The network design distinguishes between two types of cells. The first cell within each sector, $C_{0,i,j}$, functions as the coverage layer, ensuring comprehensive user connectivity. Conversely, subsequent cells, $C_{k,i,j} \forall k \neq 0$, are capacity layers, responsible for contributing additional network capacity as required. In this model, we apply multiple ESS only to the capacity layers, while the coverage layer is kept free from any ESS alterations, thus, the coverage layers are always on with all antennas powered.

Moreover, every cell C_k is allocated a total of M_k Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs). The network is populated with a maximum number of U users. We denote $\mathcal{U}_{k,i,j}^t \subset \{u_1, \dots, u_U\}$ as the set of users connected to cell $C_{k,i,j}$ at time t , ensuring that the union of all user sets is always smaller or equal to U : $|\bigcup_{\forall k,i,j} \mathcal{U}_{k,i,j}^t| \leq U$.

Let P_{TX} represent the total transmit power, distributed uniformly across each PRB in the cell. Under the assumption of maximal PRB occupancy from all cells, which equals the worst-case scenario, we can formulate the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) for a given user u_u connected to cell $C_{k,i,j}$ on any PRB. This relationship is expressed mathematically as:

$$SINR_u = \frac{P_{TX} g_{u,k,i,j}}{P_{TX} \sum_{\substack{a \in [3] \\ a \neq i}} \sum_{\substack{b \in \mathcal{B} \\ b \neq j}} g_{u,k,a,b} + N_0 BW_k} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, the numerator denotes the desired signal emanating from $C_{k,i,j}$, while $g_{u,k,i,j}$ is the channel coefficient establishing a link between $C_{k,i,j}$ and u_u . The denominator represents the total interference, where the first term corresponds to interference from all same-frequency cells excluding serving cell $C_{k,i,j}$. The second term denotes the thermal noise, with N_0 serving as the noise spectral density.

Drawing from the Shannon capacity formula, we can then estimate the maximum achievable throughput for user u_u from a single PRB. This is given by:

$$y_u = BW_k \log_2(1 + SINR_u) \quad (2)$$

This formula defines the maximum data transfer rate, y_u , that can be achieved without errors for a given SINR. It serves as an indicator for the highest achievable efficiency in our proposed system and provides a foundational basis for subsequent analysis.

We allocate a fixed service with a guaranteed bit rate (GBR), denoted by d_u to each user. Similar fixed GBR service is assumed in [15, 16]. As stipulated in the Quality of Service (QoS) characteristics of the user's assigned service, GBR must

be satisfied by the network to meet QoS requirements [17]. We operate under the assumption that user service does not necessitate additional throughput beyond the GBR, even if additional network resources are available [15]. To meet a user u_u 's GBR requirement of d_u , the average PRB requirement can be calculated as $prb_u = d_u/y_u$. Consequently, we define ideal load, denoted by $\hat{l}_{k,i,j}^t$, as:

$$\hat{l}_{k,i,j}^t = \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_{k,i,j}^t} prb_u / M_k \quad (3)$$

It's noteworthy that the ideal load is not the real cell load as it can surpass 1 when the required PRBs exceed the total available PRBs. Ideal cell load is a useful metric to show the severity of congestion in the high load range. Following this, we introduce the concept of cell load $l_{k,i,j}$, which cannot exceed 1, it is mathematically expressed as:

$$l_{k,i,j}^t = \min \left(1, \hat{l}_{k,i,j}^t \right) \quad (4)$$

Leveraging the concept of ideal cell load, we introduce the metric of unsatisfied users as a measure of the user impact during instances of cell overload. This metric shares similarities with those defined in [15, 16]. When the ideal cell load, $\hat{l}_{k,i,j}^t \leq 1$, all users can achieve their GBR and are therefore considered satisfied. However, when the ideal cell load $\hat{l}_{k,i,j}^t > 1$, M_k becomes less than the total required PRB for the users i.e. $\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}_{k,i,j}^t} prb_u > M_k$ and hence some users will be unsatisfied. Consequently, the number of unsatisfied users in $\mathcal{U}_{k,i,j}^t$, is denoted by $\hat{n}_{k,i,j}^t$, and can be articulated as follows:

$$\hat{n}_{k,i,j}^t = \max \left(0, |\mathcal{U}_{k,i,j}^t| \left(1 - \frac{1}{\hat{l}_{k,i,j}^t} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

In this work, we assume that each cell is outfitted with m-MIMO RU comprised of a 64TR (with shape 8x8) single-polarised antenna panel, as defined in [18], we formulate eight Synchronization Signal Block (SSB) beams. These beams are positioned at eight fixed horizontal azimuth directions ($[52.5, 37.5, 22.5, 7.5, -7.5, -22.5, -37.5, -52.5]$), with a uniform elevation beam angle (0) designated to all SSB beams. For the sake of simplicity, we assume that PDSCH beams for each user will align with the best-measured SSB beam for each user. This paper also considers three ESS for each cell in the capacity layer:

- 1) *Switch-off State (SOS)*: Cell is at switched off state.
- 2) *Half Power State (HPS)*: Cell radiates with half of the m-MIMO antenna elements muted (32TR).
- 3) *Full Power State (FPS)*: Cell radiates with all m-MIMO antenna elements active (64TR).

It should be noted that the overall antenna gain for beams formed from a 64TR m-MIMO antenna panel will be halved when 32 out of the 64 antenna elements are muted. Simultaneously, the total transmitted power also diminishes by half, resulting in a net loss of 6dB on the maximum gain of any beam pattern when compared to a 64TR m-MIMO antenna panel [13]. For our study, we have simplified the 32TR m-MIMO antenna model by adjusting the 64TR beam patterns by 6dB. Further, we adopt a cell power consumption model

Fig. 2: Simulation Environment

TABLE I: DRL agent training parameters

Parameter	Value
Episode Length	One week
Training Time	3 years (550368 samples)
$\epsilon_{decay}/\epsilon_{min}$	0.996 / 0.01
Learning Rate (l_r)	0.00025
Mini-batch size (N)	32
τ	1
γ	0.6
DNN θ Training Freq	every hour
Target DNN θ^- Update Freq	every week
Reward Func. parameters $\alpha/\beta/\delta$	0.001/20/0.85

[3, 7, 19] for a cell in full power state ($ESS = 2$), which, at time t , it can be described as follows:

$$P_k^{ess=2} = P_k^0 + P_k^1 l_{k,i,j}^t \quad (6)$$

Here, the first term, P_k^0 , denotes the static power consumption, which remains constant irrespective of the cell load. In contrast, P_k^1 signifies the power consumption that depends linearly on the cell load. Power consumption is directly proportional to the active number of antenna elements as specified in [13], and the total transmit power also reduces in proportion to the active antenna elements. Thus, we express the power consumption for HPS as $P_k^{ess=1} = P_k^{ess=2}/2$. Furthermore, in SOS, the cell is switched off completely, resulting in $P_k^{ess=0} = 0$.

IV. DRL BASED ALGORITHM

A. DRL Problem Formulation

In every decision-making instance denoted by T , an agent located at the gNodeB experiences a state $s^{(t)} \in \mathcal{S}$, where \mathcal{S} represents the state space. The agent then opts for an action $a^{(t)}$ belonging to the set $\mathcal{A}(s^{(t)})$, which constitutes all feasible actions in state $s^{(t)}$. The collection of all possible actions across the state space, denoted as $\mathcal{A} = \cup_{s^{(t)} \in \mathcal{S}} \mathcal{A}(s^{(t)})$, is known as the action space. The agent incurs a specific reward $R(s^{(t)}, a^{(t)})$ when taking action $a^{(t)}$ in state $s^{(t)}$, where $R: \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ signifies the reward function. Subsequently, the agent transitions to a fresh state $s^{(t+1)}$ within \mathcal{S} with a probability of $p(s^{(t+1)} | s^{(t)}, a^{(t)}) \in \mathcal{P}$. Here, $\mathcal{P}: \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ represents a probability kernel. At each interaction, the agent associates the observed state $s^{(t)}$ with a probability distribution over the action set $\mathcal{A}(s^{(t)})$. This procedure is denoted by the Markov decision process (MDP) with the 4-tuple $\langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, r, p(s' | s, a) \rangle$. The agent's *policy*, symbolised by π , designates the probability of choosing action $a^{(t)} = a$ in state $s^{(t)} = s$, and is represented by $\pi(a | s)$.

In this paper, we aim to find the policy to decide the best ESS action for the capacity cell of a single sector, given the state of the sector. The subsequent sections define the state, action spaces, and reward function related to the problem being addressed in this work.

1) *State Space*: At each decision epoch T , the agent captures a snapshot of performance metrics relevant to all cells within the sector to gain insight into the present sector conditions. The state space of this network energy consumption optimisation problem, thus, consists of all potential values that these network metrics may adopt. The specific metrics taken into account by the agent are:

- *Time Information*: Since network traffic demand strongly correlates with time, this information is essential for the agent's decision-making process. We adopt a cyclic sine/cosine transformation to encode the day of the week and minute of the day for the last 6 hours.
- *Cell Load*: The agent computes the average cell load for the previous 6 hours for all cells within the sector that is under consideration.
- *Predicted Cell Load*: The agent utilises the last 6 hours of load data to fit a linear regression model to forecast the subsequent 3 hours of load for all cells within the sector. These values are used as inputs.
- *Cell ESS*: One-hot encoded ESS of the capacity cells of the sector for the past 6 hours.

2) *Action Space*: Depending on the variations in load experienced by all cells in the same sector, the agent has the ability to choose among three ESS states (SOS, HPS, FPS) for each capacity cell ($C_{k,i,j}$ $k > 1$) as defined in Section III.

3) *Reward Function*: The reward function directs the agent's behaviour, aiming to minimise the energy consumption of each sector while ensuring there is enough capacity in the network to avoid congestion i.e. maintaining the same level of unsatisfied users. The reward function consists of two components. The first part pertains to power consumption and is defined as

$$R_{k,i,j}^1 = 2 - e^{\alpha((P_{0,i,j}^t + P_{k,i,j}^t))},$$

which diminishes exponentially with escalating power consumption, incentivising the agent to select an ESS with lower energy consumption. The second part corresponds to the high cell load region where we introduce a penalty function to deter the agent from choosing a lower energy consumption ESS. This function is defined as

$$R_{i,j}^2 = \beta \left(\max(\hat{l}_{0,i,j}, \hat{l}_{k,i,j}) \right) - \delta$$

where δ serves as the load threshold, a design parameter delineating the high load region, thereby balancing the trade-off between amplified ES and the rise of unsatisfied users. The overarching reward function is thus defined as follows:

$$R_k^t(s, a) = \begin{cases} R_{i,j}^1, & \text{if } \max(\hat{l}_{0,i,j}, \hat{l}_{k,i,j}) \leq \delta \\ R_{i,j}^1 - R_{i,j}^2, & \text{else if ESS}_{k,i,j} = \text{HPS} \\ R_{i,j}^1 - 2R_{i,j}^2, & \text{else if ESS}_{k,i,j} = \text{SOS} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

B. Deep Reinforcement Learning for Energy Optimisation

The objective of this work is to optimise ESS for the capacity cell of a given sector for ES. In the process, we leverage DRL,

and in particular, this work employs the Q-learning algorithm for the proposed solution.

In Q-learning, the agent observes the current state $s^{(t)}$ and chooses an action $a^{(t)}$ based on a stochastic policy. This work adopts an ϵ -greedy policy, where an action is chosen randomly with a probability of ϵ and the action with the highest Q-value estimate is selected with a probability of $1 - \epsilon$. The value of ϵ decays over time according to the equation $\epsilon^{e+1} = \epsilon_{decay}\epsilon^e$, where e represents the episode counter until reaches a minimum value of ϵ_{min} . After the action is executed, the agent receives a reward $r^{(t)}$ from the environment and transitions to a new state $s^{(t+1)}$. The agent aims to maximise the expected discounted reward, defined as $R_t = r^{(t)} + \gamma r^{(t+1)} + \gamma^2 r^{(t+2)} \dots$.

This work employs a DNN, denoted by θ , to parameterise the ES decision module. The purpose of θ is to map the state of the network at a specific time t , denoted as $\tilde{s}^{(t)}$, to the estimated action value of different actions $a \in \mathcal{A}$, represented as $Q_\theta(\tilde{s}^{(t)}, a^{(t)})$. Further, this work also employs an additional DNN, denoted as θ^- , which acts as a mirror to the target networks. Its function will be explained later in this section.

We use an off-policy temporal difference of 0, i.e., TD(0), for bootstrapping. As an example, the parameter updates using gradient descent can be represented by the following equation:

$$Q_\theta^{t+1}(s, a) = Q_\theta^t(s, a) + \alpha (r + \gamma \max_a \{Q_{\theta^-}^t(s', a'; \theta)\} - Q_\theta^t(s, a)) \quad (8)$$

Here, $s' = s^{(t+1)}$ and $a' = a^{(t+1)}$. After the DNN update, the target network is updated. The target networks mitigate the issue of constant movement in target estimates by delaying their updates. The target networks are updated following this rule:

$$\theta^{-(t+1)} = \tau \theta^t + (1 - \tau) \theta^{-(t)} \quad (9)$$

Here, $\tau \leq 1$ is a hyper-parameter regulating the speed of target network updates.

A memory buffer \mathcal{M} is another tool used to stabilise the network parameter updates. The memory buffer \mathcal{M} stores one-step trajectories, i.e., $\langle s, a, r, s' \rangle$. Once the memory buffer has sufficient samples, it is sampled uniformly to obtain mini-batches of size N samples, which are used to compute the loss of the Deep Q-Network (DQN) solution. This strategy reduces the correlation between contiguous samples, leading to a more stable optimisation of action selection.

DNNs θ and θ^- have identical model structure. The model structure includes three fully connected layers consisting of 512-256-64 units respectively. Each fully connected layer is followed by a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function with a negative slope of 0. For both DNNs, the ADAM solver is used with a learning rate denoted by l_r . DRL parameters are summarised in Table I.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

We utilize a simulation environment composed of $|\mathcal{B}| = 7$ gNodeBs, systematically organized in a hexagonal layout and supplemented with wrap-around functionality, ensuring the attainment of realistic SINR values, even at the boundary cells. Each gNodeB is subdivided into three sectors, with every sector encompassing two carriers. These carriers are designated as $C_{0,i,j}$ —the coverage layer operating on 850 MHz, and

Fig. 3: Average power consumption, unsatisfied users and ESS states

TABLE II: Traffic profiles used in the simulation environment

Name	Polygon	$r(t)$	$T_s/T_i/T_p/T_d$
Office	x: [-800,800,800,-800]	0.52	5/6/5/6
	y: [-200,-200,200,200]	0.052	5/6/5/6
Residential Urban	x: [-800,800,800,-800]	0.416	17/3/1/3
	y: [200,200,800,800]	0.416	7/6/4/5
Residential Rural	x: [-800,800,800,-800]	0.208	17/3/1/3
	y: [-800,-800,-200,-200]	0.208	7/6/4/5
Shopping	x: [200,600,600,200]	0.052	5/6/5/6
	y: [-600,-600,-400,-400]	0.104	5/6/5/6
Background	x: [-800,800,800,-800]	0.104	0/0/24/0
	y: [-800,-800,800,800]	0.104	0/0/24/0

$C_{1,i,j}$ —the capacity layer functioning on 2300 MHz, thereby catering to different aspects of network utility and performance.

A. Traffic Model

This simulated environment is segmented into four unique polygons, each designated with a distinct traffic profile. A traffic profile is characterized by a time-dependent user arrival rate, denoted as $r(t)$, which can be construed as superimpositions of a basic waveform as depicted in Figure 1. The user arrival rate $r(t)$ commences at T_{start} , increasing sinusoidally to peak over a duration T_i , maintaining this peak for a duration T_p , and then declining sinusoidally over a duration T_d . This design emulates real-world traffic patterns; for instance, in an area predominantly consisting of offices, $r(t)$ would ascend during morning hours, plateau during working hours, and recede during the evening and weekends.

Each user is allotted a fixed call duration and persists in the simulation until the call concludes or drops. Users are presumed stationary, initiating handovers or terminating sessions based on network modifications, namely, ES actions. Detailed parameters of each traffic profile are compiled in Table II. For each traffic profile, the first and second row on the $r(t)$ column represents the weekday and weekend $r(t)$ values during T_p . Similarly, the first and second row on $T_s/T_i/T_p/T_d$ column represents the weekday and weekend $T_s/T_i/T_p/T_d$ values.

To balance the traffic between the two carriers, Qoffset is set to -50 for capacity cells to force users to re-select to capacity cells where the measured reference signal level is greater than $Q_{rxlevmin}$ (as defined in [20]). The simulation environment with the best serving area for each carrier and polygons for each traffic pattern is depicted in Figure 2. Performance measurements from the simulation environment are collected at every 10 minutes and ESS decisions are made at every hour. The rest of the simulation settings are summarised in Table III.

B. Benchmarks

To evaluate the performance of our DRL-based solution, we compare it with three distinct alternatives:

TABLE III: Simulation Parameters

Simulation Parameter	Value
Environment Type	Hex 7
Inter-site Distance	500m
Single Antenna Element Gain	8dBi
Simulation Time	52 weeks
PRB BW / M_k	30 Khz /100 (both carriers)
Call Duration	480 sec
P_{tx}	46 dBm (both carriers)
$Q_{rxlevmin}$ [20]	$-100dBm$ (both carriers)
QOffset [20]	(0, -50) for ($C_{0,i,j}/C_{1,i,j}$)
$P_{k,i,j}^0/P_{k,i,j}^1$	360.93 /155.18 ([19])
$tron_0^0/tron_1^0/tron_0^1/tron_1^1/$	0.3/0.2/0.4/0.3

Algorithm 1: Threshold based algorithm

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 $ess_1^{t+1} \leftarrow ess_1^t$ 
if  $l_0^t \leq troff_0^0$  and  $ess_1^t \in [1, 2]$  and  $l_1^t \leq troff_1^0$  then
   $ess_1^{t+1} \leftarrow 0$ 
else if  $l_0^t \leq troff_0^1$  and  $ess_1^t = 2$  and  $l_1^t \leq troff_1^1$  then
   $ess_1^{t+1} \leftarrow 1$ 
end if
if  $l_0^t \geq tron_0^1$  and  $ess_1^t \in [0, 1]$  then
   $ess_1^{t+1} \leftarrow 2$ 
else if  $l_0^t \geq tron_0^0$  and  $ess_1^t = 0$  then
   $ess_1^{t+1} \leftarrow 1$ 
end if

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- 1) ES Disabled: All cells operate in HPS.
- 2) Threshold-Based Solution (TBS): For benchmarking purposes, we implement a conventional threshold-based solution as elaborated in Algorithm 1. Here, the ESS of $C_{1,i,j}$ at time t is denoted as ess_1^t . The superscript of the parameter represents the ESS state, and the subscript denotes the carrier. For instance, $tron_0^0$ signifies the coverage cell ($C_{0,i,j}$) threshold for power-up of the capacity cell from SOS. The $tron$ parameters are outlined in Table III, and $troff$ parameter values are computed as $troff_x^x = tron_x^x - hyst$ with $hyst = 0.1$.
- 3) Smart Energy Efficiency using DRL (SEEDRL): In this solution, a DRL agent is trained over three years of simulated time, amounting to 550,368 data samples. DRL agent training parameters are listed in Table I.

C. Results

In this subsection, we discuss results derived from running the three solutions over a 52-week span. The User Equipment (UE) arrival rates and call durations are modelled as exponentially distributed variables with the mean values specified in Table II and III respectively.

Figure 3(a) details the daily mean average power consumption for each solution, illustrating a confidence interval of 95%. When compared to scenarios with Energy Saving (ES) disabled, SEEDRL and TBS manifest an overall power reduction of 34.13% and 25.14% respectively, with SEEDRL providing an additional power saving of 8.99%.

During low-load periods, specifically between midnight and 6 AM, both TBS and SEEDRL maintain similar minimal power consumption levels. However, SEEDRL significantly surpasses TBS during the high-load daytime hours, particularly between 10 AM and 12 PM.

The principal trade-off with ES measures is in the diminished network capacity and its ensuing impact on the rate of unsatisfied users, represented daily in Figure 3(b). While the ES-disabled scenario, TBS, and SEEDRL result in 2.08%, 2.09%, and 2.17% of unsatisfied users respectively, SEEDRL exhibits only a marginal increase of 0.08% compared to TBS. The reward function of SEEDRL can be fine-tuned with design parameter δ to balance user satisfaction and power savings.

In this study, a fixed GBR service is assigned to each user. However, the framework is adaptable to multi-service environments, where the state space incorporates the total cell load from all services. Moreover, the unsatisfied users metric can be independently adjusted for each service, based on its priority, allowing for a refined management of service satisfaction levels according to operator preferences.

Figure 3(c) provides insight into the ESS distribution across capacity cells throughout the simulation. The SEEDRL solution yields 22.83% fewer ESS changes compared to TBS, indicating a significant reduction in network alterations. Additionally, both solutions displayed a higher frequency of SOS compared to HPS, with cells being switched off 70.1% and 50.3% of the time under SEEDRL and TBS, respectively. Given the reward function and corresponding thresholds, this disparity leads to longer durations of cell switch-off.

In summary, our study reveals that the considered ES solutions, particularly SEEDRL, can significantly reduce power consumption without adversely impacting user satisfaction. Additionally, the application of the mentioned solutions indicates a major reduction in the frequency of network modifications, thereby attesting to the efficiency and effectiveness of the proposed methods.

VI. CONCLUSION

We proposed a DRL-based algorithm that utilizes two ES techniques namely cell switch-off and m-MIMO muting depending on the situation. Our proposed solution SEEDRL saves power by 8.99% compared to its counterpart the TBS solution, while losing user satisfaction by only 0.08%. SEEDRL is easily customizable by making a trade-off between user satisfaction and ES. Furthermore, SEEDRL significantly reduces the number of ESS changes (22.83%), improving run-time efficiency and reducing the risk of failed implementations. In future works, we intend to extend our solution to a higher order of m-MIMO antennas for multiple levels of m-MIMO antenna muting envisioned for mmWave frequencies for 6G and beyond.

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